

The effect of bibliometric research performance assessment on the specialization vs diversification strategies of scientists

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Abstract

A possible side effect of several research evaluation schemes adopted by governments and research organizations is the discouragement of research diversification and cross-discipline fertilization, which are crucial for major global scientific challenges. This work intends to contribute to the literature stream investigating such initiatives' effects on scientists' specialization/diversification strategies. To this purpose, we analyze the response of academics to the introduction of the national scientific accreditation (ASN) for professorship introduced in Italy in 2012. We will conduct a longitudinal disciplinary analysis of the publications of each Italian professor in the sciences (over 25.000), accounting for those individual and contextual variables that might moderate the opportunistic response to the ASN incentive scheme.

Introduction

The introduction of performance-based research funding (PBRF) systems in an increasing number of countries, and the concurrent adoption of research evaluation schemes, impact the research behaviour of scientists. The outcome expected by policy-makers is, among others, improvement in research productivity and the effectiveness of recruitment and fund allocation. Often these positive effects are not disjoint from negative externalities, caused mainly by the opportunistic behaviour adopted by those subjects under evaluation who tend to maximize self-interests at the expense of societal returns (Fang, Steen, & Casadevall, 2012; Haustein S., & Larivière V., 2015; De Rijcke, Wouters, Rushforth, Franssen, & Hammarfelt, 2017). Evidence of opportunistic behavior is found for the reduction of research diversification, interdisciplinary research, or new research trajectory exploration (Hicks, 2012; Rafols, Leydesdorff, O'Hare, Nightingale, & Stirling, 2012; Wilsdon, 2016). In the worst cases, when the marginal benefits exceed marginal costs (Nagin, Rebitzer, Sanders, & Lowell, 2002), opportunistic strategies might degenerate into a range of scientific misconduct, such as salami-slicing publications, plagiarism, self-plagiarism, illegitimate self-citing, collusive cross-citing, and even scientific fraud (Sala & Brooks, 2008; Hazelkorn, 2010; Honig & Bedi, 2012; Edwards & Roy, 2017; Seeber, Cattaneo, Meoli, & Malighetti, 2019; Abramo, D'Angelo, & Grilli, 2021).

This work intends to contribute to the stream of literature investigating the effects of research evaluation initiatives on the scientists' specialization vs diversification strategies. Diversification mostly takes place through participation in interdisciplinary research which analyzes, synthesizes, and harmonizes links between disciplines into a coordinated and coherent whole. The growing complexity of global problems such as climate change, energy efficiency, pandemics, security, poverty, gender discrimination, etc., challenges scientists to integrate

perspectives, information, data, techniques, tools, concepts, and theories from different disciplines (National Academies of Science, 2005). Society then would benefit from scientists diversifying part of their research to engage in interdisciplinary projects of the kind mentioned above. Unsurprisingly, promoting interdisciplinarity in research is one of the most emphasized objectives in the European science policy: "... to foster, harness, and leverage collaborative interdisciplinarity should become a key priority for EU research and innovation policy" (Allmendinger, 2015).

Though, a side effect of several research evaluation schemes adopted by governments and research organizations, as well as of the disciplinary organizational structure and culture of research institutions and scientific societies, is the discouragement of research diversification and cross-discipline fertilization. Deciding whether to specialize instead of diversifying is a legitimate choice by scientists, consequently opting for specialization entails no marginal costs. Conversely, marginal benefits are conspicuous when scientists undergo bibliometric-based research performance evaluations. In fact, evidence was found that publications falling in the prevalent research field of a scientist on average show higher citation-based impact than those falling in other fields (Jamali, Abbasi, & Bornmann, 2020; Abramo, D'Angelo & Di Costa, 2019; Zeng et al., 2019). Furthermore, the scholars that focalize their research are those with a higher intensity of publication (Jamali, Abbasi, & Bornmann, 2020). The extent of benefits from specialized research varies across contexts depending on the research performance evaluation schemes and the incentive systems based on them.

Our study concerns the impact of the national scientific accreditation (*abilitazione scientifica nazionale*, ASN) for professorship introduced in Italy in 2012 on the academics' specialization vs diversification behaviour. Two factors embedded in the ASN make it more convenient for scientists to specialize their research: i) two out of three research performance indicators adopted in the ASN are citation-based; ii) evaluation of candidates occurs at discipline level (184 in all), by committees of full professors specialized in that discipline, and the motivation by far most frequently cited in the ASN minutes for the habilitation refusal is the incomplete fit of the candidate with the competition disciplinary sector (Abramo & D'Angelo, 2019). The Italian case then represents an ideal context to assess the effects of research performance evaluation initiatives on the opportunistic strategies of scientists about specialization vs diversification. We will adopt an after-before (ASN) disciplinary analysis of publications of Italian academics, accounting for such exogenous variables as gender, age, academic rank, research discipline, and context which might moderate the opportunistic response to the ASN incentive scheme.

The manuscript is structured as follows. Section 2 reviews the literature on the diversification vs specialization behavior of scientists, and the moderating role of personal and contextual characteristics. Section 3 provides an overview of the ASN for academic appointments. Section 4 presents the theoretical framework, methodology and dataset used for the analysis, while Section 5 shows and discusses the results obtained. Finally, Section 6 provides the authors' conclusions and comments.

Literature review

Scientists are subject to two contrasting forces, one pushing them to advance knowledge in their own field of specialization which they find more comfortable, and the other drawing them to apply their knowledge in interdisciplinary research, or to explore new fields. They often confront the dilemma of pursuing self-interest in career and reputation or the public interest in solving societal issues and circulating knowledge beyond disciplinary boundaries (Fontana,

Iori, Sciabolazza, & Souza, 2022). The researchers' starting point is always their own disciplinary expertise, while research diversification offers them an occasion to acquire and offer complementary knowledge (Schuitema & Sintov, 2017). Generally, most prominent researchers adopt a “scatter-gather” strategy, while essentially concentrating on one or two fields over their career (Chakraborty, Tammana, Ganguly, & Mukherjee, 2015). Scientists tend to perceive research diversification as risky and less productive, with personal attitudes and interests playing a role in their choices (Bateman & Hess, 2015).

The reasons underlying research diversification may be various (Belkhouja, Fattoum & Yoon, 2021 Franzoni & Rossi-Lamastra, 2017; Leahey, Beckman, & Stanko, 2017; Nagle & Teodoridis, 2019). The degree of diversification results from the interplay of individual traits (i.e. educational background, cultural values, gender, seniority, spectrum breadth featuring the perimeter of the prevalent discipline of research) and contextual characteristics (i.e. employer-type, organizational vision, scope and size of research disciplines, incentive schemes). Senior scientists and those higher in rank generally show a higher propensity to diversify (Franzoni & Rossi-Lamastra, 2017). This is not surprising as senior and high rank scientists tend to coordinate more research projects than junior researchers. Furthermore, once tenure has been achieved, professors are less afraid to adopt higher risky strategies including diversification of their research activity.

The influence of gender on research diversification is not yet consolidated across countries. Few studies have found that female scientists diversify more than males (Pinheiro, Durning & Campbell, 2022; Jamali, Abbasi, & Bornmann, 2020; van Rijnsoever & Hessels, 2011), while no correlation at all was found in the case of Italian academics (Abramo, D'Angelo & Di Costa, 2018).

It has been observed that research teams are getting larger (Cummings and Kiesler, 2014; Porter and Rafols, 2009; Stephan, 2012; Wuchty et al., 2007). Because each scientific community is limited in size by definition, it is likely that the higher the number of colleagues with which a researcher collaborates, the more diversified (less specialized) will be its research output. The degree of diversification was found to be affected by knowledge and social relatedness (Tripodi, Chiaromonte, & Lillo, 2020). When diversification implies participation in multidisciplinary teams, which is most often the case, social and geographical proximity increases the probability to meet specialists from different disciplines, to overcome cognitive distance, and to reduce the costs of communication (Rekers & Hansen, 2015). It was found also that researchers employed in the private sector tend to diversify less than academics, which is mostly due to the profit-oriented nature of private companies (Nagle & Teodoridis, 2020).

Incentive schemes definitely play a crucial role in determining the degree of specialization of researchers. Formal career progression incentives tend to emphasize the ideal of the lone scientist, publishing in top-ranked journals in the field, and being able to obtain the most selective grants. Furthermore, research specialization is often associated with the ideals of scientific rigor, while diversification is associated to applied research with dubious theory-based approaches. Research performance evaluation methods vary across disciplines. Bibliometric approaches are typical of the hard sciences but are hardly applicable to the arts and humanities which resort to peer review, while the social sciences fall in between. Cultures and expectations vary too. For example, it was shown that in Sociology, contrary to common expectations, they were the candidates with a highly diversified publication portfolio the ones with the highest probability to become an associate professor (Leahey, Keith, & Crockett, 2010).

Ascertained that incentives play a key role in the choice of specializing or diversifying the research agenda of scholars, we now turn to analyze the effects of the introduction of the Italian ASN on the research behaviour of academics.

The Italian Scientific Accreditation (ASN)ⁱ

For decades, Italian governments have made countless attempts to fight favoritism in public competitions for Italian academic positions (Abramo, D'Angelo, & Rosati, 2015; Perotti, 2008; Zagaria, 2007; Gerosa, 2001). The latest reform to that end introduced the National Scientific Accreditation (ASN), which ever since became a prerequisite to participate in competitions for associate and full professor. In 2011 and 2012, a “Regulation on awarding of national scientific accreditation”ⁱⁱⁱ and “Regulation of criteria and parameters for evaluation of candidates and verification of committee member qualifications”ⁱⁱⁱ defined the structures and operation of the ASN. The dates of these administrative acts are important in establishing the framework of our empirical investigation, as we shall see later on.

Accreditation committees would be informed for their judgment by three bibliometric indicators of research performance. For positions of associate and full professor, passing the threshold values of one, two or three (at the discretion of the single committees) bibliometric indicators^{iv} became a prerequisite for accreditation, and thus for career advancement.

According to the regulatory framework at that time, every two years the Ministry of Education, Universities and Research (MIUR) owed to issue a call for accreditations to 184 Accreditation Committees, with one committee for each Competition Sector (CS). The CSs derive from the aggregation of the so-called Scientific Disciplinary Sectors (SDSs, 370 in all), which serve in general for the classification and administration of all Italian university faculties: under this system, each professor is unequivocally classified as practicing in a specific SDS.^v The SDSs, and so also their aggregations in CSs, are grouped in 14 University Disciplinary Areas (UDAs). Of the 184 CSs, 109 are classified as “bibliometric”, and the remaining 75 as “non-bibliometric”. For the bibliometric CSs, applicant members of the accreditation committees are chosen randomly from all full professors categorized in the CS who pass all three bibliometric thresholds.

The call for candidates to accreditation was instead originally issued on an annual basis, and more recently quarterly. Applicants must apply for specific CSs and academic ranks and there is no limit on the number of CSs requested, and candidates can request accreditation for both associate and full professor at the same time. The candidatures were to be accompanied by a curriculum vitae and a list of the individual's degrees and scientific publications.

For the bibliometric CSs, the list of publications served for the calculation of the three indicators.^{vi} For the candidates to the 2012 accreditations, they were:^{vii}

- number of articles in journals over the period 2002-2012, with normalization in the case of academic seniority less than 10 years (calculated from the first year of publication);
- number of citations received for the overall scientific production, normalized for the academic seniority of the candidate;
- contemporary h-index (Sidiropoulos, Katsaros, & Manolopoulos, 2007) of the overall scientific production.

The above indicators were calculated on the basis of the publications indexed in two major bibliographic repositories: Scopus and Web of Science (WoS). Beginning from a database of all the publications entered by Italian professors over the course of 2012, ANVUR proceeded

to calculate the different indicators for all Italian full and associate professors on faculty staff and then published the median values, to serve in the selection of both the committee members and their subsequent evaluations of the applicants. In fact, failing to pass the medians of relevant distribution of bibliometric indicators, implies the stop of the evaluation process and the rejection of the application. Otherwise, the committees go on to analyse other aspects of the applicant's CV and publication portfolio.

In the 2012 first call for accreditations, there were 59,148 applications,^{viii} 55.7% of which from candidates already on faculty staff; the requests for full professor accreditation were 30.5% of the total. Applications in "bibliometrics" CSs were about 62.2% of total.

Research hypotheses, data and methods

In the light of what emerged from the literature review, the ASN evaluative framework might certainly impact the diversification vs specialization strategies of Italian researchers through at least two mechanisms. The first concerns the need to pass the bibliometric thresholds. The second concerns the need to show a scientific production aligned with the topics which characterize the CS and relevant to it. Both mechanisms lead to incentivize a specialization strategy. Therefore, we subsume two hypotheses:

Hypothesis 1. After the introduction of the ASN, assistant and associate professors in bibliometric SDSs, eager to progress in their careers, increase the specialization degree of their research agenda.

Hypothesis 2. Full professors and associate professors accredited under the first ASN stage, being subject to a weaker incentive, do not vary significantly their research orientation.

To this end, we have analyzed the specialization degree of professors in two five-year periods (2008-2012 vs 2013-2017), i.e. prior and subsequent to the introduction of ASN. The accreditation criteria and indicators were first published in June 2012, so it is reasonable to expect the first appearances of any effects on the research agenda of Italian academics in 2013.

In the next section we will provide details about the research framework designed to empirically test the above hypothesis.

Dataset

According to the database of Italian professors maintained by the MIUR,^{ix} at the end of 2012, there were 57,400 professors on staff at Italian universities, of which 35,200 belonged to bibliometric SDSs. We limit our field of observation to the assistant, associate and full professors (26,171 in all), falling in a bibliometric SDSs in each year of the period 2008-2017. Table 1 shows the breakdown of the dataset of analysis by disciplinary area, rank and gender.

We use the author name disambiguation algorithm developed by D'Angelo, Giuffrida, and Abramo (2011) for construction of the bibliometric dataset, based on the coupling of the publications extracted from the Italian National Citation Report (I-NCR) by Clarivate Analytics and the MIUR database. This algorithm^x assigns an I-NCR publication to a given professor if the latter:

- has a name compatible with one of the authors of the publication;
- belongs to one of the recognized universities in the list of addresses indicated by the authors of the publication;
- belongs to an SDS compatible with the subject category (SC) of the publication;
- was on staff at 31 December of the year prior to that of the publication.

Of the 26,171 total professors, 590 were unproductive throughout the ten year period. The remaining 25,581 produced a total of 987,339 authorship and 492,587 unique publications, distributed per UDA and period as indicated in Table 2.

Bibliometric data are arranged as a 10-year panel. The structure of the dataset is unbalanced since the dependent variable (the degree of specialization of the research portfolio of a professor) is undefined in any year when he/she has zero publications. It results that 10,286 professors have observations on all 10 years and the rest have at least one year with missing value. Overall, 204,357 professor-years are available.

Table 1: Dataset of analysis, number of SDSs, and professors[†], by UDA

UDA*	No. of SDSs	Full professors	Associate professors	Assistant professors	Total professors
1	10	697 (18.9%)	798 (40.4%)	910 (40.8%)	2,405 (34.3%)
2	8	378 (10.3%)	626 (20.0%)	611 (27.8%)	1,615 (20.7%)
3	12	457 (22.1%)	763 (43.4%)	1,013 (59.0%)	2,233 (46.1%)
4	12	160 (18.1%)	284 (31.3%)	347 (32.6%)	791 (29.2%)
5	19	807 (32.2%)	1,082 (47.9%)	1,696 (64.7%)	3,585 (52.3%)
6	50	1,489 (14.2%)	2,225 (25.6%)	3,463 (40.2%)	7,177 (30.3%)
7	30	590 (16.3%)	794 (36.5%)	1,024 (48.2%)	2,408 (36.5%)
8	9	327 (7.6%)	409 (17.1%)	404 (30.9%)	1,140 (19.3%)
9	42	1,203 (7.4%)	1,387 (16.4%)	1,377 (20.5%)	3,967 (15.1%)
11	8	230 (44.3%)	271 (60.1%)	349 (64.8%)	850 (57.8%)
Total	200	6,338 (17.1%)	8,639 (31.3%)	11,194 (43.5%)	26,171 (33.1%)

* 1 - Mathematics and computer science, 2 - Physics, 3 - Chemistry, 4 - Earth sciences, 5 - Biology, 6 - Medicine, 7 - Agricultural and veterinary sciences, 8 - Civil engineering, 9 - Industrial and information engineering, 11 - Psychology

[†] Counts refer to academic ranks and SDSs as of 31/12/2012. In brackets, the share of females

Table 2: Authorships and publications of professors in the dataset by disciplinary area, UDA

UDA*	2008-2012		2013-2017	
	Authorship	Publications	Authorship	Publications
1	21017	15652	25472	19525
2	67986	22019	102995	24936
3	42376	23631	49859	28319
4	7760	5378	11488	7803
5	47560	30231	57221	37088
6	124216	67840	167062	90835
7	24239	13661	34405	19719
8	9467	6831	16989	12301
9	64453	43065	95848	65508
11	6236	4635	10690	7984
Total	415310	211103**	572029	281484**

* 1 - Mathematics and computer science, 2 - Physics, 3 - Chemistry, 4 - Earth sciences, 5 - Biology, 6 - Medicine, 7 - Agricultural and veterinary sciences, 8 - Civil engineering, 9 - Industrial and information engineering, 11 - Psychology

** The value is lower than the column total due to publications authored by professors from different UDAs.

The statistical model

Measuring the specialisation degree of professors

To measure the degree of specialisation of a professor and how this may have varied over time and, in particular, following the introduction of ASN, we will make use of an indicator called “specialization index” (SI), defined as the share of total publications of a professor falling in his/her prevalent SC. In turn the prevalent SC is identified as follows: i) we identify the scientific production of the scientist over a period of time; ii) we associate each of his/her publications indexed in the Web of Science (WoS) with the SCs of the hosting journal; iii) we identify the SC with the largest number of the scientist’s publications. Such SC represents the “prevalent” field of research of the scientist. As an example, consider the case of one of the co-authors of this paper. Over the 2013-2017 period, his scientific production sums to 55 publications. The analysis of the SCs associated with the journals hosting these works shows the following:

- Information science & library science: 49
- Computer science, interdisciplinary applications: 42
- Computer science, information systems: 3
- Education & educational research: 2
- Environmental studies: 2
- Management: 2
- Public administration: 2
- Economics: 1

So the most frequent SC is “Information science & library science”, associated to 49 of his 55 works, either alone or with other SCs^{xi}. Note that professors with multiple prevailing SCs are randomly assigned to one among those with a higher frequency.

In formulae, the specialization index of professor i in the year t , as:

$$SI_{i,t} = \frac{\# \text{pubb}_{i,j,t}}{\# \text{pubb}_{i,t}} \quad [1]$$

Where

$\# \text{pubb}_{i,j,t}$ = Number of publications in SC j , authored by professor i in year t ;

$\# \text{pubb}_{i,t}$ = Total number of publications authored by professor i in year t ;

j = the prevalent SC of professor i considering all his/her publications in the $[t-2; t+2]$ five year period.^{xii}

Going back to the co-author of the present work, considering that over the 2013-2017 period, 49 out of his 55 total publications were in “Information science & library science” journals, we can conclude that his $SI_{2013-2017}$ is equal to $49/55=89.1\%$.

The independent variables and target covariates

The simple variation in the degree of specialization in the years following the introduction of the ASN is not sufficient evidence that there has been a casual effect of the ASN on the research agenda of Italian academics. Testing the research hypotheses requires identification and control for other variables expected to impact as well the dependent variable, as evidenced in the above review of the literature, including:

- 1) *The number of publications the researcher publishes in a given year.* We assume a relationship between the annual output of a researcher and the degree of specialisation of his/her production in that year. In particular, a higher intensity of publication could imply a higher specialization degree.
- 2) *The field of research.* The degree of specialization of a scholar depends on the spectrum breadth featuring the disciplinary perimeter of the SDS in which she works. In the Italian

academic system, some SDSs are very broad (FIS/01-”Experimental Physics”, for instance), others are much less so (VET/04-”Inspection of food of unusual origin”).

- 3) *The average number of co-authors of the researcher’s publications.* Each scientific community is limited in size by definition, so the higher the number of colleagues with which a professor collaborates, the more diversified (less specialized) his/her research output is likely to be.

Among the personal and contextual factors that could affect the specialization vs diversification strategies, we consider:

- 4) *Academic rank.* We assume that an assistant professors tends to specialise more than a full professor who typically coordinates the work of different teams.
- 5) *Age.* We assume that, on average, researchers tend to specialize in the early stages of their careers and to diversify later on.
- 6) *Gender.* We assume that, on average, females tend to specialize more than males.

Finally, also the context plays a role:

- 7) *Context.* We assume that the context in which a researcher operates influences the choices regarding the spectrum of his/her research interests. Specifically, the marginality or predominance of the SDS in the territory where the professor operates. We chose to model such variable as the ratio between the number of colleagues in the professor’s SDS and the total number of professors working in universities in the same city.

The target covariates, namely the covariates related to our research hypotheses, are:

- *PostASN:* a time-varying dummy variable taking value 0 until 2012 and value 1 from 2013.
- *StatusASN:* a time-constant variable with four categories, according to the strength of the ASN incentive to change research strategy, from low to high:^{xiii}
 - *Associate professors accredited in ASN 2012:* having obtained accreditation for full professor, these have no need of further participation in ASN;
 - *Full professors:* they do not participate in the ASN, however they can apply for joining evaluation committees; in this case they must meet bibliometric thresholds, similar to but slightly different from those for accreditation candidates.
 - *Assistant professors accredited in ASN 2012:* having obtained accreditation for the role of associate professor, they remain motivated to participate in future ASN calls for full professor.
 - *Assistant and associate professors not accredited in ASN 2012:* professors who either did not participate or participated and failed, and would therefore be motivated to participate in future ASN calls.

In the model, *PostASN* is interacted with *StatusASN* so that the change in the specialization degree after 2012 is estimated separately for each category of *StatusASN*.

We fit a linear random effects model on panel data, since we intend to test our research hypotheses controlling for some covariates, some of which are time invariant. Specifically, the response variable y_{it} is the share of publications for professor i in year t , falling in his/her prevalent SC for which we specify a log-linear regression model:

$$\log y_{it} = \beta_1 x_{1it} + \beta_2 x_{2it} + \dots + \beta_p x_{pit} + v_i \quad v_i \sim N(0, \sigma^2) \quad [2]$$

The model has p covariates, which may be time-varying, plus a random effect v_i collecting time-constant unobserved factors of professor i . Fields effect are controlled through dummies associated to each SDS.

Estimation is performed with the random effect “xtreg” command of STATA.

Results

First we present the descriptive statistics of the empirical analysis, then the inferential statistics aimed to test the research hypotheses.

Descriptive statistics

The descriptive statistics for the time-varying variables (2008-2017) are reported in Table 3, and for the time-constant variables in Table 4.

Table 3 shows that in the period considered the specialization index is on average 0.602, i.e. on average 60.2% of publications of each professor in each year falls in his/her prevalent SC. The trend is decreasing (Figure 1), while the number of professors with at least one yearly publication is increasing.

Table 3 shows also that some of the independent continuous variables (*Number of publications* and *Number of co-authors*) are right skewed, due to a low number of very highly productive scholars and to mega-authorships (mainly in Physics publications). Also the “Context” variable presents a significant skewness. Indeed, these variables enter the model after a logarithmic transformation. The age varies between 28 and 76, with an average of 51. For binary variables the mean is equivalent to the proportion, thus the value for *PostASN* (0.512), indicates that there are slightly more observations after ASN. The values of *Rank* reveal that assistant and associate professors have nearly the same weight (respectively 38.6% and 35.2%), whereas full professors are the smallest group (26.2%).

Table 3: Descriptive statistics for time-varying variables in the period 2008-2017 (204,357 professor-years)

<i>Variable</i>	<i>Min</i>	<i>Max</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Std Dev.</i>
Specialization index	0	1	0.602	-
Number of publications	1	177	4.831	7.487
Number of co-authors	1	2897	23.014	167.428
Context	0	0.833	0.014	0.017
Age	28	76	51.070	8.235
PostASN	0	1	0.520	-
Rank				
Assistant	0	1	0.386	-
Associate	0	1	0.352	-
Full	0	1	0.262	-

Figure 1: Time plot of the observations in the dataset (204,357 professor-years in all) and average yearly specialization index

As for time-constant variables, Table 4 shows that 32.2% of the professors are female. The distribution of the key variable *StatusASN*, combining the rank of the professor before ASN and the outcome of ASN, shows the prevalence of not accredited assistant or associate professors (49.4%). Full professors represent 23.9% of total observations, followed by accredited assistant professors (15.9%), and accredited associate professors (10.7%).

Table 4: Descriptive statistics for time-constant variables (25,581 professors)

<i>Variable</i>	<i>Min</i>	<i>Max</i>	<i>Mean</i>
Female	0	1	0.322
ASN status			
Full professor	0	1	0.239
Associate professor accredited in ASN 2012	0	1	0.107
Assistant professor accredited in ASN 2012	0	1	0.159
Assistant or associate professor NOT accredited in ASN 2012	0	1	0.494

Inferences from the statistical model

We run two models. The first one (Model 1) concerns all independent variables but *StatusASN*, and it will be used to check for the effects of control variables, and observe the general trend of the response variable. Next, we will introduce in the model also the dummies associated to the *StatusASN* variable (Model 2), in order to test our research hypotheses.

Table 5 reports the estimates of the parameters of Model 1 from the random effects panel regression, omitting those less relevant, i.e. the baseline rates and the coefficients of the 200 dummies for the SDSs.

The variables considered are all significant. For the variables specified through dummies, the coefficients reported in the second column can easily be associated with marginal effects. For instance, the value 0.00226 for the coefficient of “Gender - Female” means that considering two professors with identical values of all covariates, except for gender, a female professor has a specialization index 0.226%^{xiv} higher than a male professor. With a *z* statistic equal to 3.05 and a *p*-value of 0.002, the effect can be considered statistically significant at an α level of 0.05.

At the same time, as expected, the effect of the academic rank is also significant, indicating a degree of specialisation that decreases with higher academic rank. Age also plays a significant role: the marginal effect is small, as for other covariates, but an interesting effect emerges: the positive sign of the coefficient indicates that, all else being equal, younger people appear to be less specialised than their older colleagues. Concerning the effect of productivity (in this case simply referred as the number of publications produced in the year), the first row of Table 5 shows an effect aligned with what previously assumed and stated. Professors with a higher output show a higher degree of specialisation. In contrast, for the variable “No. of co-authors” the effect is negative: belonging to a scientific network with a larger size leads to a greater diversification of the research topics addressed (coef. -0.01366). The most important effect, however, is attributable to the “Context” variable: being institutionally framed in a field (SDS) relevant in size with respect to the overall research staff in a city, leads to greater specialisation. That is, operating in a field with few or no other colleagues in one’s own city evidently leads the professor to open up to interdisciplinary collaborations and, consequently, to diversify his/her scientific activity. Finally, the value of the coefficient associated to the target variable *PostASN* indicates a significant reduction in the average specialisation degree in the five-year period after the introduction of the ASN. The year-by-year figures are reported in Figure 2 which shows a decreasing trend that becomes very evident after 2012.

Table 5: Estimates of the main parameters of the panel random effect model for the analysis of the specialization index of Italian professors – Model 1

	Coef.	Std Err.	z	P>z	Coef.	[95% Conf. Interval]
Publications	0.00834	0.00086	9.74	0.000	0.0067	0.0100
No. of co-authors	-0.01366	0.00116	-11.77	0.000	-0.0159	-0.0114
Context	0.23097	0.05983	3.86	0.000	0.1137	0.3482
<i>PostASN</i>	-0.00957	0.00049	-19.58	0.000	-0.0105	-0.0086
Age	0.00018	0.00005	3.42	0.001	0.0001	0.0003
Gender						
Male	(baseline)	-				
Female	0.00226	0.00074	3.05	0.002	0.0008	0.0037
Rank						
Full	(baseline)	-				
Associate	0.00204	0.00080	2.55	0.011	0.0005	0.0036
Assistant	0.00442	0.00097	4.54	0.000	0.0025	0.0063
cons	0.18473	0.00534	34.58	0.000	0.1743	0.1952

Estimates obtained controlling for field effects (200 dummies associated to SDSs)

Number of obs = 204357; Number of groups = 25581

σ_u : 0.0395; σ_e : 0.0909; ρ : 0.1588

R-sq: within = 0.0043, between = 0.2101, overall = 0.0803

Wald chi2(209) = 10672.68, Prob > chi2=0.0000

Figure 2: Time plot of coefficients of year dummies introduced in Model 1 regression in place of PostASN

In order to test for our research hypotheses, we run a second regression model (Model 2), similar to the previous one, but substituting:

- “Rank” with “*StatusASN*”
- “*StatusASN*” with an interaction between “*StatusASN*” and “*PostASN*”.

The results are shown in Table 6 and indicate that the control variables considered in the previous model act in the expected directions and their effects remain essentially unchanged, with the only exception of “Age”, that is no longer significant.

Instead, talking about the target variables, we observe that:

- The coefficients of *StatusASN* concern the specialization index of the three status categories regardless of ASN. Adjusting for the control variables, compared to full professors (reference category), the only significant coefficient is the one related to not accredited professors (0.00606); this category of academics show a comparatively higher degree of specialisation (coef. 0.00606).
- The coefficients of *PostASN* x *StatusASN* measure the change, for each category of *StatusASN*, in the specialization degree after the introduction of the ASN. All categories show a significant decrease in specialization, more evident for professors not accredited in the 2012 ASN (-0.01255), followed by full professors (-0.00783), accredited associate professors (-0.00700), and accredited assistant professors (-0.00607).

Therefore, controlling for the available covariates, all professors reduced their degree of specialization after the introduction of the 2012 ASN. The magnitude of such a decrease seems to be related to the ASN status. In particular, the category most sensitive to the incentive embedded in the ASN (not yet accredited professors), actually shows almost twice as much variation as the others.

Table 6: Estimates of the main parameters of the panel random effect model for the analysis of the specialization index of Italian professors – Model 2

	Coef.	Std Err.	z	P>z	Coef. [95% Conf. Interval]	
Publications	0.00856	0.00087	9.84	0.000	0.0069	0.0103
No. of co-authors	-0.01363	0.00116	-11.75	0.000	-0.0159	-0.0114
Context	0.23383	0.05985	3.91	0.000	0.1165	0.3511
Age	0.00007	0.00005	1.4	0.160	0.0000	0.0002
Gender						
Male	(baseline)	-				
Female	0.00234	0.00075	3.14	0.002	0.0009	0.0038
<i>StatusASN</i>						
Full	(baseline)	-				
Associate accredited	0.00139	0.00130	1.07	0.286	-0.0012	0.0039
Assistant accredited	-0.00069	0.00133	-0.52	0.603	-0.0033	0.0019
Not accredited	0.00606	0.00108	5.61	0.000	0.0039	0.0082
<i>PostASN x StatusASN*</i>						
Full	-0.00783	0.00082	-9.57	0.000	-0.0094	-0.0062
Associate accredited	-0.00700	0.00108	-6.46	0.000	-0.0091	-0.0049
Assistant accredited	-0.00607	0.00097	-6.25	0.000	-0.0080	-0.0042
Not accredited	-0.01255	0.00078	-16.12	0.000	-0.0141	-0.0110
_cons	0.18960	0.00533	35.59	0.000	0.1792	0.2000

* *PostASN=0 as baseline, aiming at estimating the effect of the ASN introduction on the degree of specialization of professors in each of the four StatusASN considered.*

Estimates obtained controlling for field effects (200 dummies associated to SDSs)

Number of obs = 204357; Number of groups = 25581

σ_u : 0.0395; σ_e : 0.0909; ρ : 0.1589

R-sq: within = 0.0047, between = 0.2094, overall = 0.0803

Wald chi2(209) = 10673.18, Prob > chi2=0.0000

Discussion and conclusions

This work falls in the stream of research investigating possible negative effects of performance-based incentive schemes. In particular, it focuses on the changes in the specialization/diversification strategies of academics in response to performance evaluation. Opportunistic responses are expected to be commensurate with the benefits embedded in the incentives, which are not necessarily the same across the academic population, and with personal and contextual features playing a role in such responses.

Results show a significant reduction in the average specialisation degree of academics after the introduction of the Italian ASN, reinforcing a trend already occurring before the ASN.

The degree of specialization decreases as the academic hierarchy increases, in line with Franzoni and Rossi-Lamastra (2017) who found the same phenomenon in the field of Physics. Quite interestingly, we found also that younger academics, all other features being the same, result as less specialised than their older colleagues. Furthermore, we found that higher publication intensity is associated with a higher degree of specialization, confirming the occurrence of a “productivity penalty” associated with inter-disciplinary research as revealed also by Leahey, Beckman and Stanko (2017). Conversely, being part of large scientific networks leads to a greater diversification of the research topics addressed. Evidence of a growing trend in research collaboration, as confirmed by the growing number of co-authors of publications (Cummings and Kiesler, 2014; Porter and Rafols, 2009; Stephan, 2012; Wuchty et

al., 2007), is certainly related to the trend of increasing diversification degree that we observed for Italian academics in the period analysed.

Differently from other studies' findings (Pinheiro, Durning & Campbell, 2022; Jamali, Abbasi, & Bornmann, 2020; van Rijnsoever & Hessels, 2011), in Italy female professors tend to specialize more than male colleagues. Contrasting results may be due to specific differences in attitudes of Italian female academics or in methodologies employed in the studies on the topic. The major determinant of the academics specialization degree is found to be the context in which the scholar operates, namely the number of colleagues of the same field *vis a vis* those in different fields, which affects the opportunity to collaborate. We know in fact that social and geographical proximity affect the probability to meet specialists in a given field (Rekers & Hansen, 2015).

Turning to our main research question, that is whether professors increased their degree of specialization as an opportunistic response to the introduction of the ASN, the answer is no, which is counter-intuitive. All categories of professors decreased their specialization degree, continuing a trend already existing before the introduction of the ASN. Surprisingly though, it was the category more sensitive to the ASN incentive scheme (assistant and associate professors not yet accredited), the one that, all others equal, increased more than any others its diversification degree. Explaining this phenomenon is not easy. Results may be distorted by few limitations in the statistical model adopted: i) not all contextual variables were considered, for example counter-specialization incentive systems such as national and international calls funding interdisciplinary research projects; ii) omitting considering the evolution of social factors (knowledge and social relatedness) which impact on the engagement in interdisciplinary research (Tripodi, Chiaromonte, & Lillo, 2020); iii) the difficulty of modelling additional personal features, such as curiosity, open-mindedness, etc.; iv) the bias embedded in considering static field-classification schemes in contrast with the rapid evolutionary dynamics of science.

Aside from possible limitations in the model, it must be said that the category more sensitive to the ASN incentive was the one originally most specialized, therefore it had more margin of diversification. Another reason might be that in the pursuit of increasing their number of publications, assistant and associate professors not yet accredited joined interdisciplinary research teams. Finally, we wonder whether scholars in the fields other than bibliometrics are aware that diversification leads to publications that on average have a lower impact (Jamali, Abbasi, & Bornmann, 2020; Abramo, D'Angelo & Di Costa, 2019; Zeng et al., 2019). If they are not aware of it, the reason for finding specialization convenient, in relation to the ASN bibliometric thresholds, decays.

Future research might delve into the specialization degree of accredited academics *vis a vis* not accredited ones, to assess whether evaluation committees favoured diversification in their subjective judgement. It would also be interesting to analyse the phenomenon at field level to assess behavioural differences across fields. Finally, while findings are not immediately generalizable to other countries, it would be useful to compare the responses to similar incentive schemes in other cultural contexts.

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Notes

ⁱ The description that follows includes text from a previous publication (Abramo & D'Angelo, 2015).

ⁱⁱ Presidential decree 222 of 14/09/2011.

ⁱⁱⁱ Ministry of Education, Universities and Research Ministerial decree 76 of 07/06/2012.

^{iv} Initially the regulations required achievement of thresholds in all the three indicators, but after heated debate this was modified in consideration of the conditions of different sectors.

^v The reason for introducing the CSs, unifying two or more SDSs into a single CS, is probably to reduce the number of accreditation committees, and therefore evaluators. SDSs were unified based on cognitive proximity and number of professors falling into them.

^{vi} For the “non-bibliometric” CSs, the indicators were not based on citations.

^{vii} For applicants to positions as committee members, the indicators were number and impact of overall scientific production, without normalization for years of academic seniority.

^{viii} Such data were retrieved from the ASN pages of the MIUR website <http://abilitazione.miur.it/public/candidati.php?sersel=50&>, but are no longer available. Subject to regulation, the ministry withdrew most data 60 days after the committee decisions, leaving only the publication of the lists of successful candidates

^{ix} For each professor this database provides information on their name and surname, gender, affiliation, SDS and academic rank, at close of each year. <http://cercauniversita.cineca.it/php5/docenti/cerca.php>, last accessed on 29 March 2023.

^x The harmonic average of precision and recall (F-measure) of authorships, as disambiguated by the algorithm, is around 97% (2% margin of error, 98% confidence interval).

^{xi} The sum of the values referred to the listed SCs is above 55, due to publications hosted in multi SCs journals.

^{xii} We observe a five-year period to avoid the random fluctuations of yearly observations.

^{xiii} To build the variable *StatusASN*, we take the academic rank in 2012, just before ASN. If the professor has no record in 2012 (due to no publication in that year), we take academic rank in the last observed year. Note that the dataset does not consider whether an assistant professor would be seeking accreditation for advancement to associate or full professor, however the latter case would be so rare that it can be ignored.

^{xiv} $0.226\% = \text{EXP}(0.00226) - 1$